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Executive summary

The HEAP Microbiomics data analysis work package (WP9) provides analysis tools to perform both metagenomics and metatranscriptomics.

Metagenomics is the field comprising studies on non-host genomics. If we are to analyse a human specimen, metagenomics will investigate all DNA present in the specimen that is not human. DNA can belong to bacteria, fungi, archaea, and viruses. Metagenomic analysis of DNA tells what DNA organisms are present and provides molecular characterisation.

Metatranscriptomics is related to the RNA present that is unrelated to the host. Metatranscriptomics will provide information about RNA organisms (metagenomics can identify RNA viruses, for example) and those whose genome is a DNA molecule but that is transcribing (replicating).

Both fields are essential, as some microorganisms can “only” be present (DNA) but not replicate (RNA). RNA presence is typical for human cancers with a microorganism-agent aetiology.

The WP9 focuses on metagenomics and metatranscriptomics analyses of DNA/RNA sequences from different datasets in the HEAP’s Information Commons (IC). At this moment, we analyse data from TCGA [2] (a well-known and validated public database “The Cancer Genome Atlas”, <https://www.cancer.gov/tcga>), the Swedish cervical screening cohort (comprising more than 0.5 million specimens from women invited to the organised screening program in Sweden), the Finnish Community Randomised trial of HPV Vaccination, which initially involved 80 000 adolescent boys and girls and the Finnish Maternity Cohort dataset of about 1 million Finnish women with linkable diseases associations available.

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1. Introduction

The HEAP Microbiomics data analysis work package (WP9) provides analysis tools to perform both metagenomics and metatranscriptomics.

Metagenomics is the field comprising studies on non-host genomics. If we are to analyse a human specimen, metagenomics will investigate all DNA present in the specimen that is not human. DNA can belong to bacteria, fungi, archaea, and viruses. Metagenomic analysis of DNA tells what DNA organisms are present and provides molecular characterisation.

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Both fields are essential, as some microorganisms can “only” be present (DNA) but not replicate (RNA). RNA presence is typical for human cancers with a microorganism-agent aetiology.

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Information Commons (IC). At this moment, we analyse data from TCGA [2] (a well-known and validated public database “The Cancer Genome Atlas”, <https://www.cancer.gov/tcga>), the Swedish cervical screening cohort (comprising more than 0.5 million specimens from women invited to the organised screening program in Sweden), the Finnish Community Randomised trial of HPV Vaccination, which initially involved 80 000 adolescent boys and girls and the Finnish Maternity Cohort dataset of about 1 million Finnish women with linkable diseases associations available

In our previous report, we presented a CNN-based, well-performing classifier that reached an F1 score of 0.84 for the training set and 0.85 for the validation set. As entry data dehumanised TCGA data, HPV positive and negative from *cervix uteri* and *endometrium* have been used. The main challenges described in the previous report were scarcity of computational resources, type of available entry data (imbalance HPV positive > HPV negative) and uncertainty regarding the type of features the network recognises.

Here, we addressed these issues. First, we gained access to the Mahti CSC cluster, significantly improving computational resources. Secondly, we investigated the impact of the sequence length on the CNN performance. The classifier's performance depended strongly on the sequence length, with longer sequences 48/49 bp classified exclusively as non-viral and shorter sequences classified prevalently as viral.

We tried to overcome this problem with different strategies. First, given that padding may be a feature recognised by the CNN, we used two different padding techniques: 1. repetition of the currently read line with a single padding character between repetitions until SEQ_LEN is complete and 2. concatenating subsequent lines (without padding) until SEQ_LEN is full and cutting out such a fragment for learning. However, CNN has still differentiated the sequence length instead of the characteristic features of the sequences.

We addressed the length problem in the second step by improving the training dataset. We extracted 220 *Human papillomavirus* viral sequences from the PAVE database (<https://pave.niaid.nih.gov/>). The lines were concatenated and then divided into 80-character long reads, so padding was necessary only for the last read in case the sequence was shorter than 80 characters. As 220 virus sequences did not generate enough positive data, we multiplied the reads 80x by forgetting the consecutive letter from the sequence. However, this approach also failed to detect the virus sequences in the validation dataset.

In the third approach, we used a Jaccard/Tversky index for the data analysis instead of CNN. The Jaccard/Tversky index is an asymmetric similarity measure of the intersection of sets A and B divided by the power of the sum of sets A and B. Because set A ("human" sequences) is large and would have a lot of shingles, it does not match a few shingles from the HPV viruses. To address this issue, only a subset of viral-like sequences was kept when reading through the human data due to the computational resources. The next step was "jaccard_bis", so instead of holding $\#A_cup_B$ in the denominator, there is just $\#B$. This way, it is checked how much of the HPV virus is in the human sequence.

The results differed from the BLAST in some cases, but the Jaccard/Tversky index was low. The entry sequences have been set into 18-element shingles (18 is a number selected experimentally) and put into the shingles set separately for each virus variant. The network was trained again. The process required extensive computational resources, especially the division into shingles.

To sum up, the previously presented CNN distinguished sequence length rather than specific sequence features. To obtain results not based on the sequence length, we changed the strategy, learned the model from real viral sequencing and real human data, and applied the model based on the data analysis. We will continue assessing the latter technique and check possible ways to improve the network for distinguishing specific viral sequences.

1.1 Computational resources

Detecting virus sequences in human DNA sequences is challenging regarding computational resources. The input data is big, the sequences are long, and the analysis requires significant CPU time. The HEAP project integrates different data through a common software platform (PaaS) based on the Hopsworks technology. Hopsworks manages computational resources in the Hadoop-like model. In this deliverable, we used ICM HPC-type resources with high availability of GPUs to accelerate the workflow of implementing, training, testing and validating the machine learning model for metagenomics/transcriptomics analysis. In this deliverable, we focus on demonstrating the running metagenomics workflows using traditional, HPC-type resources.

In this deliverable, we used different HPC resources provided by the project partners:

1. **Mahti** - cluster provided by CSC.
Total of 1404 CPU nodes and 24 GPU nodes. Both CPU and GPU nodes have two AMD Rome 7H12 CPUs with 64 cores each, making the total core count about 180 000. The CPUs are based on AMD Zen 2 architecture, supporting the AVX2 vector instruction set, and run at 2.6 GHz base frequency (max boost up to 3.3 GHz). The CPUs support simultaneous multithreading (SMT), where each core can run two hardware threads. When SMT is enabled, the total thread count per node is 256 threads. The CPU nodes have 256 GB of memory and no local disks. The GPU nodes have 512 GB of memory and a local 3.8 TB Nvme drive. They also have four Nvidia Ampere A100 GPUs.
2. **Puhti** - cluster provided by CSC.
In total, there are 682 CPU nodes, with a theoretical peak performance of 1.8 Petaflops. Each node is equipped with two latest generation Intel Xeon processors, code name Cascade Lake, with 20 cores each running at 2.1 GHz (Xeon Gold 6230). Compute nodes have a mix of memory sizes: i) 192 GB on 564 nodes, ii) 384 GB on 100 nodes, with 40 also sporting a 3.2 TB NVMe disk for fast local storage, iii) 768 GB on 12 nodes, iv) 1.5 TB on 6 nodes. Interconnect network HDR InfiniBand by Mellanox, nodes connected with 100Gbps HDR100 links and 4.8 PiB Lustre parallel storage system by DDN.
3. **okeanos** - Cray XC40 cluster provided by ICM.
Total 1084 nodes, no GPU cards. Nodes are equipped with Intel Xeon E5-2690 v3 processors running at 2.6 GHz. Each node has 128 GB memory and can run 24 physical threads (or 48 logical threads in multithreading).
4. **rysy** - GPU cluster provided by ICM
A total of 6 nodes are equipped with Intel Skylake processors and 380 GB RAM. Nodes are equipped with 4 Nvidia GPU V100 32GB nodes.

The HEAP project used the above systems through a batch queueing system, such as the SLURM job management system installed at each node.

2 HPV and Biopipeline for metagenomic data

As described in previous deliverables, the WP9 aims to provide several pipelines for metagenomic (DNA) and metatranscriptomic (RNA) analysis that are user-friendly, open-source and generic to widen the spectra of possible users, enabling scientists with different research questions and datasets to use them.

Researchers interested in studying the microorganisms within a sample can use these pipelines and bioinformatic tools independently of the research purposes or dataset.

2.1 HPV-meta

The research team from Karolinska led by Sara Arroyo Muhr provided an open-source bioinformatics pipeline, “HPV meta”, that detects HPV transcripts in RNA sequencing data, including several steps to warn operators of possible viral contamination.

This pipeline was already described in D9.3. Briefly, the pipeline starts with pre-processing the sequencing files, followed by an HPV detection using non-human high-quality reads. Once the detection is done, a post-analysis that includes the cut-off settlement (validation, 10 reads and 690 bp coverage to make an HPV call) and a fasta sequence generation for HPV-positive samples is run (Figure 1). HPV meta was validated using the whole TCGA dataset (10,908 bam files comprising around 90 terabytes of sequencing data), and the code is publicly available (<https://github.com/hpvcenter/HPV-meta>). It is implemented in the Spark-Hadoop environment but can also be used in other environments. The pipeline is fully implemented in HEAP Hopsworks, and its detailed description can be found in the journal Scientific Reports in July 2022 [1].

Figure 1 HPV-meta:

2.2 Biopipeline: fully available in the HEAP platform with novel features

The research team from Karolinska provided another open-source bioinformatics pipeline, “Biopipeline”, at the end of 2022. This pipeline performs a taxonomy classification of all the non-host genomes in one specimen. The BIO pipeline enables researchers to identify and classify all known bacteria, viruses and fungi in the biospecimens (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Biopipeline:

As described in D9.3, Bio-pipeline is based on the same principles as HPV-meta (user-friendly, open-source and generic) and includes three main steps: pre-analysis, taxonomic classification, and post-analysis. The Biopipeline was validated using the TCGA database, a sub-dataset (800 samples) of the cervical screening cohorts, colorectal specimens from the TCGA, and the datasets from our partners from Finland and Stanford.

The Biopipeline was partly implemented in the HEAP platform, with all the steps needed except for the post-analysis scripts, due to the lack of R studio in the Hopsworks platform.

Since the last deliverable, we have had great support from WP6 and implemented the full post-analysis inside the HEAP platform. Currently, R scripts can easily be implemented in Jupyter notebooks, and the pipeline can, therefore, fully run in the HEAP platform.

Furthermore, based on other researchers' needs, we have implemented a new tool that can be incorporated into Biopipeline. We included a differential abundance analysis. This analysis is performed as part of the post-analysis in R. It aims to find the enriched species. Authors can, for example, visualise if a species is more enriched in specific tumours compared to healthy. We implemented the Biopipeline, including this new feature in the study of metagenomics and metatranscriptomics of colorectal cancer. The results

have been recently published in Cancer Medicine. (2) This feature can generate both tables with the species enriched, the log-fold change and adjusted p-values (Figure 3), as well as heatmaps (Figure 4). An example can be seen in Figures 3 and 4 (manuscript under draft writing status).

Figure 3 Differentially abundant species among colorectal tumours and colorectal healthy tissue from immunocompetent patients sorted by FDR adjusted p-value:

Family Genus Species (NCBI ID)	Taxonomic group	log2 fold change	p-value	FDR adjusted p-value
Bacteroidales-Bacteroidetes-Bacteroidia-Bacteroidia (279344)	Bacteria	-2.240214	0.0000000015561	0.00000001985
Fusobacteriales-Fusobacteria-Fusobacterium (261)	Bacteria	4.137005	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lachnospirales-Bifidobacteriales-Bifidobacterium (28210)	Bacteria	-3.204011	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lancefieldiaceae-Bifidobacteriales-Bifidobacterium (45604)	Bacteria	-4.125095	0.000000000000001	0.0000000000001
Bacteroidales-Bacteroidetes-Bacteroidia-Bacteroidia (279344)	Bacteria	-2.649565	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lachnospirales-Coprococcaceae-Coccus (28005)	Bacteria	-4.056274	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lachnospirales-Streptococcaceae-Kummelsoxia (10000)	Bacteria	-2.645100	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Ustilaginomycetes-Pezizomycotina-Graesslinia (200016)	Fungi	1.7014720	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Oribacteriales-Oribacterium-Oribacterium (200016)	Bacteria	-2.436754	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lachnospirales-Streptococcaceae-Streptococcus (200016)	Bacteria	-2.545767	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lachnospirales-Verrucomycota-Prothothaca (200016)	Bacteria	-2.315555	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lachnospirales-Oribacterium-Oribacterium (200016)	Bacteria	-2.407032	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Fusobacteriales-Fusobacterium-Fusobacterium (200016)	Bacteria	3.830195	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lachnospirales-Roseburia-Roseburia (200016)	Bacteria	-2.458019	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Oribacteriales-Oribacterium-Oribacterium (200016)	Bacteria	-2.431003	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lancefieldiaceae-Bifidobacteriales-Bifidobacterium (45604)	Bacteria	-2.091002	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lachnospirales-Oribacterium-Oribacterium (200016)	Bacteria	-2.303004	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lachnospirales-Coprococcaceae-Coccus (200016)	Bacteria	-2.205767	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Fusobacteriales-Fusobacterium-Fusobacterium (200016)	Bacteria	3.272004	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lachnospirales-Streptococcaceae-Kummelsoxia (10000)	Bacteria	-2.570005	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Lachnospirales-Bifidobacteriales-Bifidobacterium (45604)	Bacteria	-2.250010	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Corynebacteriales-Corynebacterium-Corynebacterium (200016)	Bacteria	2.110000	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Chaetomiales-Heterobasidium-Heterobasidium (200016)	Fungi	0.800000	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Nectriales-Nectria-Nectria (200016)	Fungi	-0.800000	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Ophiocordales-Phragmotrypa-Phragmotrypa (200016)	Fungi	-0.700000	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985
Herpesvirales-Herpesviridae-Herpesvirus (200016)	Virus	-1.600000	0.000000000000001	0.00000001985

Figure 4 Heatmap for differentially abundant bacterial species when comparing colorectal tumours (Tumor) and colorectal healthy tissue

(Mucosa) from immunocompetent patients. All species reported had an FDR-adjusted p-value <0.01.

2.3 Decontamination:

Several recent studies have used FFPE blocks for microbiome characterisation but with warnings about the considerable microbial contamination of those materials when compared with fresh-frozen tissue due to an increased manipulation of samples. Since many FFPE blocks exist for cancer diagnosis and, therefore, probably subjected to higher contamination rates than fresh-frozen samples, we aimed to develop a tool to clean up potential specific contaminants before their microbiome analysis.

Decontamination uses a two-step validation approach that looks for potential systemic contaminants and possible carry-over during laboratory procedures. This new tool was validated using an FFPE dataset, including tumours and blank controls. The Decontamination package is now included as an extra feature for the Biopipeline and will be soon published (manuscript under draft writing status). The results show how decontamination is needed when performing metagenomics/metatranscriptomics with FFPE material. It also highlights the robustness of Biopipeline and how it can be used with different types of specimens.

3. CSC pipelines and ML analysis for metagenomic data

The research team from Oulu University (UOULU) in Finland led by Ville Pimenoff in collaboration with Stanford, provide bioinformatics pipelines, “CSC pipelines” for microbial taxa or functional group classification, *de novo* assembly and phylogenomic described here and in D5.3.

The Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM) at the University of Warsaw, led by Piotr Bala, provided an HPV prediction tool using Machine Learning to classify HPV virus based on the viral DNA/RNA sequence. The model is implemented in Hopsworks as described in deliverable D9.2.

3.1 CSC microbial pipeline

The research team from Oulu University (UOULU) in Finland provides bioinformatics pipelines, “CSC pipelines”, that include comprehensive classification of microbial taxa or their functional groups in metagenomes and meta-transcriptomes [3,4,5,6]. Theoretically, the pipelines can be used in DNA and RNA sequencing data, although RNA should not be treated the same way for biological data integrity as DNA. The pipelines involve the baseline of pre-processing of the raw sequence data, removing human-derived reads if necessary and the classification of all possible microbial taxa or their functional groups and estimating the detected compositions of the taxa/functional groups and their likely false-positive signals in the data. Stemming from previous and current work in HEAP [6,7,8], it is important to note that the advanced *de novo* pipelines for PEMs DNA/RNA deep metagenome sequence data analyses are described separately in WP5.3 by HEAP participants UOULU and Stanford for CSC.

The CSC pipelines leverage the Puhti and Mahti computational resources as well as ePouta in CSC and use different metagenomic tools when feasible for preprocessing (Trimmomatic, BBtools), mapping (bwa, bowtie) and classifying reads (Kraken/kraken2/Metaphlan/Human2) from the available sequence data (DNA/RNA) and implementing R scripts for differential analysis and plotting of the obtained compositional microbial taxa (diversity and distribution across the datasets) and phylogenomics of the abundant taxa. An important part of the pipeline is carefully estimating the likely false positive signals in the metagenomic microbial taxa distribution.

Figure 5 provides the schematic workflow for the CSC pipeline:

A concise summary of the workflow in its most important steps is below

- Prepossessing: Single or pair-end FASTQ files are taken as input files. FASTQ-file is a file type typically provided by most current sequencing methodologies. FASTQ files are quality trimmed, including deduplication of likely PCR biases using Cutadapt, Trimmomatic, Picard or BBtools, depending on the data requirements. Typically, only a quality score of 20 (Q20) high-quality reads is retained.
- If human reads need to be removed, users can filter them out using fast K-mer-based filtering or mapping human reads using bwa or bowtie.
- Classification of the high-quality reads: Pre-processed single or paired-end metagenome and meta-transcriptome sequences are classified using two different classifiers: kraken/kraken2 derived k-mer matching algorithm) and MetaPhlan2 (a marker-gene mapping algorithm) with a large, curated reference database for bacteria, viruses, fungi, protozoa and archaea available (updated

in November 2023). Microbial functional groups are classified using the HUMAnN2 algorithm.

- Quality control and normalisation: Output of classification of taxa and functional groups is checked for likely environmental contamination and outliers in the dataset. Further data normalisation and transformation for compositional analysis are performed.
- Results estimations and plotting: Distribution of microbial taxa across the dataset and stratified diversity estimations are plotted using R and further used for likely phylogenetic inference of particular microbial taxa (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Distribution of microbial taxa across a dataset based on species taxa abundance (A) or ranking (B).

These pipelines were originally used to validate and analyse microbial taxa from human stool and gut biopsies [4,5] and oral/cervical swab samples [6]. The pipelines and related tools are available in the CSC computational environment and currently in GitHub (<https://github.com/PimenoffV>) and soon also be available in the HEAP GitHub repository. Work is to be done to implement the results obtained from the pipelines for advanced ML analysis in the Hopsworks platform.

During the BYOD event held in Stockholm in November 2022, the pipeline was available to HEAP partners to test at the CSC cluster. In addition, the partners from Finland and Stanford validated their advanced pipelines described in WP5.3, confirming the coherent results and using them for parallel pipeline analysis for the PEMs wearable dataset. These PEMs RNA/DNA metagenomic analyses are currently ongoing for pilot data (N=100). Nevertheless, the CSC microbial pipeline described here has

already been validated using a large deep-sequenced metagenome dataset (N=1600,[5]) and the related R codes for estimating ecological diversity distributions [7]. Further implementation of the results from the CSC pipelines to be analysed with the efficient and integrated machine learning tools in Hopsworks is currently ongoing and described in detail in WP6.3 as ML for metagenomic microbial data, which is also demonstrated in WP6.4.

3.2. Recent developments in deep learning and virus sequence detection

The major issues regarding the detection of viruses with standard alignment techniques have already been described in the previous reports. We have also described the architecture and approach applied in older neural networks, such as ViraMiner (Tampuu et al., 2019) that rely on a combination of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and dense neural networks, VirNet (Abdelkareem et al., 2018) relying on the CNN model and Vira Pipe (Maarala, A.I. et al. 2017) that is based on the artificial neural network and random forest algorithm. Here we present recently published networks that detect viruses based on the deep learning models (Wani et al. 2022):

1. EdeepVPP (Dasari and Bukya, 2022)
This is a CNN-LSTM-based model. What is new the model can extract the underlying patterns that work like significant features for better classification. AUC is around 0.9.
2. Deep VirFinder (Ren et al., 2020)
The model is based on CNN architecture and trained, tested, and validated the data from 2,314 reference genomes (of viruses infecting prokaryotes from the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). DeepVirFinder achieved AUROC 0.93, 0.95, 0.97, and 0.98 for 300, 500, 1000, and 3000 bp sequences respectively. The highest AUROC was achieved when using the model trained by 150 bp sequences
3. RNN-VirSeeker (Liu et al., 2022)
The network is based on the recurrent neural network architecture with LSTM cells, and identifies viral short-length sequences. Thanks to the LSTM architecture, the algorithm can remember the position of every base in the sequence. Also, there are several gates to remember which parts of the sequence should be remembered and which are forgotten; therefore, this strategy decreases computational

resources. Another benefit is that the model can learn well from the limited reference sequences in the training database.

4. VirSorter 2 (Guo et al., 2021)

VirSorter2 is based on extracting 27 features from each sequence fragment for classification. The F1 score also surpassed 0.8 for the viruses underrepresented in the viral databases, which is not the case for other classifiers. VirSorter2 was also able to minimise errors associated with atypical cellular sequences, including eukaryotic genomes and plasmids.

5. Vir Hunter (Sukhorukov et al. 2022)

the model combines a CNN-based module covering different k-mer sizes with a downstream random forest classifier module. Performs well in the detection of novel viruses.

6. DETIRE (Miao et al., 2023)

DETIRE performs well on short viral sequences (less than 1000 bp). In this model, a graph-based nucleotide sequence embedding strategy is utilised to enrich the expression of DNA sequences by training an embedding matrix. Then, the spatial and sequential features are extracted by trained CNN and BiLSTM networks, respectively, to enrich the features of short sequences. Finally, the two sets of features are weighted combined for the final decision. The network is trained on the 220,000 sequences of 500 bp subsampled from the Virus and Host RefSeq genomes.

3.2. Preprocessing and padding

Deep-learning algorithms require entry sequences of the same length. Since the input sequences for our model vary, the implemented solution is to pad the end of each sequence with zero to a fixed length (padding).

Padding is a standard technique used in machine learning. However, little is known about the impact of padding on the performance of the networks. Padding can be applied to DNA, RNA, and protein sequences. It is also commonly applied in the preprocessing strategy using One-hot encoding.

Only recently has the impact of padding on the performance of networks been investigated. To our knowledge, only one paper shows the impact of different padding on the network's performance in different tasks for the application in biology (Lopez-Del Rio et al. 2020). The authors have tested

seven types of padding using three different deep-learning architectures in a hierarchical enzyme classification problem. Different network architectures have been investigated (only feed-forward neural networks (only_denses), feed-forward neural networks coupled with a convolutional layer (1_conv), and feed-forward neural networks coupled with a stack of convolutional layers (stack_conv) and different padding types (mid-, strf-, rnd-, and zoom-) and they classified them along with the known types (pre-, post-, and ext-) into dense and sparse paddings. Dense paddings are those keeping zeros together in a block (pre- at the beginning, post- at the end, mid- in the middle, and ext- at both ends), while in sparse paddings, zeros are interspersed on the sequence (randomly in the case of rnd- and uniformly for strf-) or amino acids are duplicated (zoom). The task for this study was a hierarchical classification of enzymes with two levels: the first is a binary classification of proteins into enzymes/non-enzymes (task 1), and the second is a multi-label prediction of the enzyme type (task 2). For task one, only dense padding showed the best performance, but it was unclear for the other architectures. Also, the distribution of activation showed differences for the sparse and dense padding. For the dense padding type, there is no difference in performance between types of dense padding. However, switching to sparse padding decreases the performance.

There is no data on the padding in DNA and RNA, which should be further investigated. When we tested the network's performance, it looked like the CNN might recognise padding (sequence length) instead of nucleic acid viral features. Therefore, we tested different types of padding.

3.3. Explaining the performance CNN

CNNs are often criticised for their black box approach, meaning that it is impossible to assess the values that impact the classification. However, in recent years, this problem has been overcome with several methods:

SHAP- Shapley Additive exPlanations. It's a way to calculate the impact of a feature on the value of the target variable. Each feature is considered a player, and the dataset is a team. Each player gives their contribution. The sum of these contributions gives us the target variable's value given some features' values (i.e., given a particular record). We are working on applying this approach to the network.

Explainable CNN- the explainable CNN has been published by (Dasari and Bukya, 2022). The authors identified several DNA motifs detected as viral. The learning capacities were obtained as follows: After completion of

training, the filters become learned filters, which means the filter updates weights to optimum values. The authors have developed a computational step-by-step approach to identify the underlying patterns that guide the prediction of viral sequences, as shown. For the viral genome prediction, we have extracted the motifs with higher activation values than the threshold (half of the highest activation value) from the human metagenomic dataset. The activation value of the pattern depended on the work performed by different filters over the input sequences. Filter jobs could catch highly relevant structures. The authors have considered one motif from each filter with the highest activation value. The motifs ACGACCG, ACGCAGT were extracted by filters 2 of the filters and were biologically relevant motifs for identifying viral sequences.

In our model, due to the data imbalance, an application of accard/Tversky index greatly improved algorithm recognition of the viral sequences.

3.4. Impact of padding on the network

At the beginning of work on D9.4, the convolutional network model created in the previous deliverable was exported to the Mahti CSC cluster. The dehumanised TCGA data from the Hopsworks cluster was also copied to this cluster. The model was then loaded, and predicted viral sequences were evaluated on real data. The model was trained on data for which the site of resection or biopsy was cervix uteri and endometrium. In total, there are 894 samples (files) with these data.

Figure 6 Number of reads

The results are generally close to 1 for shorter reads and near 0 for longer ones. The border line is slightly fluid, but 1 is not returned for reads longer than 49 characters, and 0 is not returned for reads shorter than 31 characters, although the number of reads of 31 to 48 characters for which 0 is returned is relatively small (logarithmic scale). Hence, the "limit" is about 48/49 characters. A single read was no longer than 76 characters, and therefore, the input to the neural network was set to 80 characters.

Our first thought was that the data on which the model was learning was too small - 9 positive and negative sample files, whose data in archived format occupied less than 35 MB. Hence, the model was retrained on a larger amount of data. Nevertheless, when making predictions, the model returned a prediction greater than 0.5 for most reads that were less than 48 characters long. The hypothesis was that the model learned to distinguish long and short lines (lines with more padding), as the provided data and expected result correlate in that manner. To final check this hypothesis, the following tests were performed: lines longer than 48 chars were truncated to 48 chars – for this test, all reads were treated as viral sequences (prediction value greater than 0.5).

As a result, we have decided to investigate the possibility of using a different way of dealing with data for which the read length is smaller than the input for the neural network. In other words, we have checked other ways of dealing with short reads, as is also discussed in the literature (*Lopez-Del Rio, Angela et al.2020*))

We have checked these two methods:

1. repetition of the currently read line with a single padding character between repetitions until SEQ_LEN is full
2. connecting subsequent lines (without padding) until SEQ_LEN is full and cutting out such a fragment for learning (what remains is the beginning of the next learning sequence)

For a faster evaluation of the network's correctness, 4 characteristic samples with known results were selected: for which the length of most reads is 76 and 48, and for which a virus was found and not found. These files are: "sample_05483.fq.gz", "sample_00058.fq.gz", "sample_00064.fq.gz", and "sample_00005.fq.gz".

Unfortunately, for both padding techniques, the results were also incorrect. Namely, it was not possible to distinguish between samples containing viral sequences and those that did not.

It turned out that the neural network constructed in this way cannot distinguish between samples that have a read with viral data from those that do not have virus genes. Indeed, there are very few virus genes in the input sequences from the dehumanised TCGA samples – in the test files, only some of the reads are actually viral sequences of the sample, and they are among the non-viral sequences – the network could not distinguish between them.

3.5. The problem of detecting the length of the sequence as a key feature

To overcome this problem, we have prepared the model using better-prepared data. Instead of using sequences where the virus was found, we used virus sequences available in the NIAID NIH Database (specifically, the genome of human *papillomavirus* in FASTA format from https://pave.niaid.nih.gov/search/search_database). Using that data, we created an input dataset that returns *True* (positive set) and the samples without HPV as *False* (negative set).

For learning purposes, these sets should have similar sizes in terms of the number of reads. However, the virus sequences are rather small – the FASTA file with all 220 HPV virus variants is about 1.7 MB. Moreover, lines for each virus sequence have 60 characters. To create reads without adding padding, lines for each variant are concatenated and then divided into 80-character long reads; padding is necessary only in the last read, which is probably not 80-character long.

The number of reads was still low. We have decided to generate more reads in the following way: we *forgot* one or more letters (Nucleic Acid Codes) from the beginning, and then we create new sequences by dividing the sequence into 80-character long reads. To illustrate with an example: the starting sequence was ATCGAGCT... and by skipping one character, we make the following sequences: TCGAGCT... , CGAGCT..., GAGCT..., etc.

In this way, we can increase the sequence set size to almost 80 times, but compared to TCGA data, it is still a small set of HPV-positive sequences – the set of negative reads is much larger. We have decided to trim negative reads set to the number of generated positive reads. In theory, it is possible to create more reads by performing random mutations of viral sequences, e.g., randomly replacing letters, cutting out gene fragments, duplicating fragments, and changing the order. However, this was not done, as a convolution neural network should handle this.

Additionally, to minimise the negative set size, instead of mixing "*cervix uteri*" and "*endometrium*", we have taken only samples with resection place from "*cervix uteri*" as a negative set.

We created network layers in the source code in the following way:

```
keras.layers.Input(shape=[SEQUENCE_LEN, 6]),
keras.layers.Masking(mask_value=padding_mask.numpy()),
keras.layers.Conv1D(FILTERS, KERNEL_SIZE, activation='relu'),
keras.layers.SpatialDropout1D(rate=DROPOUT),
keras.layers.MaxPool1D(KERNEL_SIZE),
keras.layers.Conv1D(FILTERS, KERNEL_SIZE, activation='relu'),
keras.layers.SpatialDropout1D(rate=DROPOUT),
keras.layers.MaxPool1D(KERNEL_SIZE),
keras.layers.Flatten(),
keras.layers.Dense(FILTERS, activation='relu'),
keras.layers.Dropout(rate=DROPOUT),
keras.layers.Dense(1, activation='sigmoid')
```

The capital case variables are parameters, and different values were used to prepare various models. The best network model was prepared for the following parameters (job-2392931 - disk model size: 1.4G):

- SEQUENCE_LEN=80
- HPV sequence repeat with: `int shift(SEQUENCE_LEN/5)`
- DROPOUT=0.0
- FILTERS=128*8*4
- KERNEL_SIZE=5
- Total params: 117,579,777

We have used keras EarlyStopping callback to finish learning, where the model is no longer updating:

```
Restoring model weights from the end of the best epoch: 12.  
2999/2999 - 84s - loss: 0.1061 - accuracy: 0.9635 - precision: 0.9542 -  
recall: 0.9755 - val_loss: 0.2453 - val_accuracy: 0.9238 - val_precision:  
0.9325 - val_recall: 0.9176 - 84s/epoch - 28ms/step  
Epoch 15: early stopping
```

Unfortunately, on the selected 4 samples, the network was unable to detect the virus, so that it was recognised in the data:

```
/sample_05483.fq.gz True 0 [531166 40607 25118 19149 16833 15376 15979 17882  
86642 37594]  
/sample_00058.fq.gz False 0 [255968 15311 9717 7462 6769 6621 6524 7415 40796  
21497]  
/sample_00064.fq.gz False 0 [132843 5185 2720 1933 1445 1413 1416 1431 6663  
2962]  
/sample_00005.fq.gz True 0 [85056 2994 1562 1095 940 849 828 855 4026 2121]  
/hpv_viruses.fq.gz None 9 [ 86 72 75 73 103 111 157 220 3945 15931]
```

We have decided to change the approach to virus detection. Instead of utilising the convolutional neural network, a mechanism from data analysis was used - the Jaccard/Tversky index.

The algorithm in this approach is presented here:

1. HPV samples are combined as before - each creates a separate sequence.
2. We divide the sequences stepwise (every 1 character) into 18-element shinglets (18 is a number selected experimentally) and put them into the shinglets set separately for each virus variant.
3. We load samples (fq.gz files decompressing them on the fly), creating one long sequence (ignoring the fact that some lines are shorter - we just connect them as if there were no holes)
4. We split the samples into shinglets and store only those that are in the virus shinglets (without this, the memory runs out quickly)
5. After reading the sequence, we calculate the Jaccard index for pairs, where one element is the individual sets with HPV (A). The other is the set of sample shingles (B) - this way, we get the index of similarity between the samples and HPV (calculated as the quotient of the power of the product of sets A and B and the power of the sum of A and B: $\frac{\#A \cap B}{\#A \cup B}$).
6. Once we have the index, we can determine which virus is most similar in the sample and mark the sample as containing the virus. In general, there will be some similarity with each virus, so we cut off

the similarity below 0.1 - we treat values below as not having a virus and above as having it.

This approach gave us the same viruses found in the CSV metadata of the samples in most cases. The results were different in some cases, but the Jaccard/Tversky index was very low in those cases.

The single-threaded solution on the Mahti server processed the aforementioned 894 files in 300m 49.430s, which gives about 20 seconds for one sequence (loading, shingleting, comparing). The shingleting procedure is the most time-consuming thing there.

Due to the successes in this field, using the shinglet length set to 18, we have decided to train the network again: we ran a train on the network, where the SEQUENCE_LEN is the smallest possible, for which a given KERNEL_SIZE (18) can be used.

Figure 7 Experimentally best working pipeline based on the alternative approach to the data analysis.

Summary of results below:

```

- (job-2464956, KERNEL_SIZE=18, SEQ_LEN=647)
Epoch 19/140
Restoring model weights from the end of the best epoch: 14.
61/61 - 7s - loss: 0.0909 - accuracy: 0.9698 - precision: 0.9796 - recall:
0.9750 - val_loss: 0.0629 - val_accuracy: 0.9753 - val_precision: 0.9727 -
val_recall: 0.9907 - 7s/epoch - 119ms/step
Epoch 19: early stopping

/scratch/project_2002659/heap-tcga-files/sample_05483.fq.gz True binary 0
[86169 2784] [0.96870257 0.03129743]
/scratch/project_2002659/heap-tcga-files/sample_00058.fq.gz False binary 0
[40090 2288] [0.94600972 0.05399028]
/scratch/project_2002659/heap-tcga-files/sample_00064.fq.gz False binary 0
[14570 1119] [0.92867614 0.07132386]
/scratch/project_2002659/heap-tcga-files/sample_00005.fq.gz True binary 0
[10475 693] [0.93794771 0.06205229]
/scratch/project_2002659/heap-tcga-files/hpv_viruses.fq.gz None binary 1 [
151 2406] [0.05905358 0.94094642]

```

Further, we tried to optimise the CNN. Unfortunately, increasing KERNEL_SIZE did not clearly indicate in which sample the virus can be found.

Using the model trained in task 2464956 on Mahti (the model takes 3.6 GB), in which there are 4096 filters, kernel_size=18 and SEQ_LEN=647, we combined lines with sequences into one long string, and then divided according to SEQ_LEN, for which the network looks like this :

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #	Trainable
masking (Masking)	(None, 647, 6)	0	Y
conv1d (Conv1D)	(None, 630, 4096)	446464	Y
max_pooling1d (MaxPooling1D)	(None, 35, 4096)	0	Y
conv1d_1 (Conv1D)	(None, 18, 4096)	301993984	Y
max_pooling1d_1 (MaxPooling1D)	(None, 1, 4096)	0	Y
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 4096)	0	Y
dense (Dense)	(None, 4096)	16781312	Y
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 1)	4097	Y
=====			
Total params: 319,225,857			
Trainable params: 319,225,857			
Non-trainable params: 0			

For the trained CNN we obtained the following results:

Restoring model weights from the end of the best epoch: 14.
 61/61 - 7s - loss: 0.0909 - accuracy: 0.9698 - precision: 0.9796 - recall: 0.9750 - val_loss: 0.0629 - val_accuracy: 0.9753 - val_precision: 0.9727 - val_recall: 0.9907 - 7s/epoch - 119ms/stepch 19: early stopping

The time for accomplishing the task took: 4min 15 s
 However, the task waited in the queue much longer than it too it to be accomplished.

Next, we predicted on all dehumanised files for which "site_of_resection_or_biopsy" is either "Endometrium" or "Cervix uteri" (job-2492160 on mahti). The results are presented in Figure 8.

For results where the expected result in CSV is True (or False), there is a slightly different prediction distribution for individual sequences in the files. The network showed the ability to learn the prediction. However, we are still working on finding the right threshold for the sensitivity.

Figure 8

Our approach has several limitations. First, we have not been able to optimise the threshold yet. Furthermore, the currently processed scripts did not take into account that the HPV file contains sequences with the letters W and Y (wildcards meaning W=[AT], Y=[CT] and N=unknown; only 1 W once, Y 3 times and N 1 time). N is repeated 1362946 times in dehumanised files but without other wildcards.

3.6 Imbalanced dataset and analysis with Jaccard/Tversky index.

The Jaccard similarity index (sometimes called the Jaccard similarity coefficient) compares members for two sets to see which members are shared and which are distinct. It is considered a measure of similarity for the two data sets, with a range from 0% to 100%. The higher the percentage, the more similar the two populations. If two datasets share the exact same members, their Jaccard Similarity Index will be 1. It can perform badly in the small datasets. The Tversky Index (TI) is an asymmetric similarity measure that is a generalisation of the dice coefficient and the Jaccard index.

This method has been applied in CNNs in the image analysis for a pixel when data are imbalanced in the image analysis. In a mask where 90% of the pixels are 0s and only 10% are 1s, the network receives a low loss even if it misses all the 1s, which means the network is not learning anything. Application of the Jaccard/Tversky index has been described for the first time in a 3D fully convolutional deep network by Salehi et al. (2017) to

obtain the most desirable performance for multiple sclerosis lesion segmentation, a typically class-imbalanced problem.

3.7. Practical application of the Jaccard/Tversky index in our pipeline

In the original idea, Jaccard/Tversky index is the power of the intersection of sets A and B and divided by the power of the sum of sets A and B. Because set A ("human" sequences) is large and would have a lot of shinglets that do not match HPV viruses, the modified version works better. We created one HPV-only super-set from the HPV-containing files - then, by reading the human data, we can see if it looks like a virus shinglet, and if so, keep it. Now, set A is actually a subset of A containing only fragments that look like viral fragments. The calculation of the $\frac{\#A_{cap_B}}{\#A_{cup_B}}$ index is the same. Of course, if we enlarge the set of viruses, the sum in the denominator would be larger and larger, so the similarity would become smaller and smaller. For this reason, the next change is `jaccard_bis`, so instead of holding $\#A_{cup_B}$ in the denominator, we just have $\#B$. This way, we check how much HPV virus is in our human sequence.

We reached a much better separation (although it does not take into account the ambiguity of specific nucleotides), but there are samples that fall between True and False, for example:

```
file min max label CSV-virus detected
sample_00500 0.0467 0.0800 False HPV146REF nan
sample_04700 0.0536 0.0808 False HPV118REF nan
sample_03529 0.0560 0.0930 False HPV146REF HPV98
sample_02987 0.0440 0.1016 False HPV146REF nan
sample_02192 0.0274 0.0852 True HPV52REF HPV52
sample_00887 0.0189 0.1011 True HPV133REF HPV133
sample_02167 0.0465 0.1203 True HPV38REF HPV38
```

The calculations were performed on full sequences. Unfortunately, due to the timeout, they did not fit within two days - 130 of the available 200 files were reviewed.

In the case of dehumanised data, all 200 files were processed in a reasonable time (job-80697 took less than 38 minutes), and the separation was much easier because so many files do not have similarities.

To speed up the calculations, we used automata - trees with shinglets (ngrams). We optimised the computational speed by using different

programming languages, obtained the best results in terms of speed with Python, and optimised the code in Java. Still, we faced the problem that some sequences are processed significantly slower than others.

The last implemented network was efficient, but during the testing phase, it probably distinguished a wrong parameter: the sequence length. Changing the padding strategy, filling in the data without her and training with a larger dataset did not overcome this problem well. The total changing of the strategy and learning from the real viral sequencing and real human data showed better results than dehumanised data from both HPV-positive and HPV-negative. Still, nothing Google or others have published on this could help distinguish the parameters. The results improved by introducing an alternative data analysis method (Jaccard Tversky index) instead of the traditional CNN.

We will still work on assessing the latter technique and check possible ways to improve the network in terms of distinguishing specific viral sequences.

4. Conclusions

The metagenomic pipelines and machine learning algorithms provided by the WP9 are user-friendly, open-source and generic tools that researchers can reuse and adapt for their data analysis.

Until 2023, the Karolinska team has provided tools for HPV detection and taxonomic analysis.

Since then, the Institute Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM) has validated additional bioinformatic features for microbiome analysis, including differential abundance analysis and decontamination of putative contaminants. All tools and pipelines have been implemented within Hopsworks 3.0. Future work will be dedicated to novel discovery and machine-learning models for disease and cancer prediction.

Until 2023, the Finnish team and Stanford, including CSC and related WP5 and WP10, have provided substantial computational resources, guidance and a set of pipelines for comprehensive DNA/RNA deep sequence data analysis. The pipelines are flexible for parameter selection for different types and quality of metagenome and meta-transcriptome datasets. Currently, the Finnish team is documenting the pipeline setups for different data types and building a tutorial to be released for open-source availability for others to implement full or parts of the CSC pipeline in other platforms,

including Hopsworks. Further novel publications such as [7,8] are expected during 2024 from implementing the CSC pipelines and further ML inferences in Hopsworks to identify exposure factors, which may enable accurate cancer predictions from longitudinal metagenomes.

The ICM provided a machine-learning model for classifying the HPV virus based on viral DNA/RNA sequences. The model was implemented in Hopsworks and trained and tested with TCGA specimens already subjected to the pre-analysis step. Currently, the team will focus on testing the model with raw data (human sequences included) and a different dataset (2400 cervical screening samples). If the model can predict HPV in the whole sequence, it means that the model can be trained with short sequences (no human sequence). It is relevant considering that training the model with long sequences is computationally intense and requires many resources and time.

Testing pipelines with different datasets helps to validate and improve the pipeline toward more accurate results. The results improved by introducing an alternative data analysis method (Jaccard Tversky index) instead of the traditional CNN.

Future plans include “tweaking” the algorithm for cancer prediction. HPV is known to cause cervical cancer, but that doesn’t mean everyone positive for HPV will develop cancer. With the large cervical screening cohort from Sweden, HPV status and the patient metadata, the aim is to predict who will develop cancer.

We will still work on assessing the latter technique and study possible ways to improve the network in terms of distinguishing specific viral sequences.

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